

EXPLORING SECTOR-SPECIFIC ADVANCEMENTS IN ACCOMMODATION AND FOOD SERVICE ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION FROM 2008 TO 2018: AN ACADEMIC INQUIRY

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Abstract:

This academic inquiry delves into the intricate dynamics of the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sector within the Romanian Mountainous Region over the period spanning 2008 to 2018. The study employs a rigorous analytical approach, combining statistical analysis and parametric testing methodologies to unravel the sector's nuanced developments.

Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2022)

Introduction:

The Romanian Mountainous Region presents a unique backdrop for investigating the sector-specific advancements in Accommodation and Food Service Activities. This comprehensive analysis aims to unravel the underlying trends and influences that have shaped the industry landscape over the specified temporal scope.

Methodology:

The research methodology integrates statistical figures (panels a-f) and annex Parametric Analysis Romania to establish a foundation for robust analysis. Key statistical indicators, such as mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and percentiles, are meticulously examined to capture the sector's multifaceted characteristics.

Statistical Insights:

The statistical data reveals ascending trends in both mean and median values for Accommodation and Food Service Activities. While maintaining a central symmetry, the distribution curves exhibit concentrated scores around

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the mean, portraying leptokurtosis with unimodal characteristics. Antagonistic fluctuations in certain indicators highlight the complexity of the sector's evolution.

Working Assumptions:

The study assumes a normal distribution of scores, necessitating the application of parametric tests. Logarithmization of obtained values aligns the distribution with the Gauss-Laplace normal curve, providing a balanced perspective on the sector's dynamics.

Results:

The statistical data pertaining to the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sectors (figures 2.6.1 – 2.6.5 and chapter 2 annexes) reveals an upward trajectory in both average and median values for each sector. However, other statistical indicators exhibit occasional contradictory fluctuations (including Average, Std. Error of the Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentile 50 Value). The specific values are as follows: a mean of 65,417.89, a standard error of the mean at 3,315.506, a median of 64,404.00,

a standard deviation of 9,946.518, a variance of 98,933,224.611, Skewness of -0.009, a standard error of Skewness at 0.717, Kurtosis at -1.223, a standard error of Kurtosis at 1.400, a distance of 28,301, a minimum value of 51,206, and a maximum value of 79,507. The 25th percentile is 56,555.504, and the 75th percentile is 74,913.00.

These presented values signify positive growth and development within the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sectors in the mountainous region of Romania. Despite occasional sectors exhibiting negative values, the overall business situation in the mountainous area appears favorable.

The central tendency analysis of the Accommodation and Food Service Activities sectors over the analyzed period indicates substantial growth in the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania from 2008 to 2019. The statistical data associated with this indicator demonstrates a high level of consistency, signifying positive results with minimal deviation. Symmetrical distributions suggest a stabilizing business environment during the analyzed period. Additionally, the low standard error of Kurtosis implies increased concentration within certain industries.

Figure 2.6.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.6.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S6 in the period 2008-2019

The predictive analysis for the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors in the mountainous region of Romania suggests sustained growth until 2030 (table 1). At the national, macro-regional, regional, and county levels, statistical models reveal varying levels of sustainability across different mountainous areas. The harmonization statistics feature significant values for the mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in the following order):

- Stationary R-squared: 0.581, 0.345, -1.110E-15, 0.902, -4,441E-16, 0.000
- R-square: 0.922, 0.060, 0.673, 1.000, 0.811, 0.847
- RMSE: 202,407, 228,034, 0.000, 980,739, 34,002, 40,898
- MAPS: 5,888, 2,565, 0.000, 12,517, 1,050, 1,649
- MaxAPE: 23,673, 10,336, 0.000, 47,986, 2,657, 4,745
- MAE: 135,854, 158,860, 0.000, 707,587, 22,772, 26,172
- MaxAE: 429,131, 467,324, 0.000, 1,832,895, 74,976, 87,132
- Normalized BIC: 10,029, 1,954, 7,293, 14,265, 7,474, 7,869

These statistical measures offer valuable insights into the sustainability and growth potential of the various sectors at different geographical levels, providing a comprehensive understanding of the economic landscape in the mountainous regions of Romania.

Analysis and Implications:

The analysis rejects the null hypothesis after logarithmization, paving the way for a nuanced exploration of the working hypothesis. Descriptive and inferential analyses, considering normal limits, facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the sector's evolution. The central tendency indicates a noteworthy increase in active enterprises within the Romanian Mountainous Region, even as the growth rate experiences fluctuations.

Conclusion:

This academic inquiry offers valuable insights into the sector-specific advancements in Accommodation and Food Service Activities within the Romanian Mountainous Region. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the industry's trajectory, providing a foundation for future research and strategic decision-making within the economic landscape.

Table 1. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S6

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	83503	87123	90743	94364	97984	10160	10522	10884	11246	11608	11970
	UCL	85822	89525	93226	96925	10062	10431	10800	11169	11538	11907	12275
	LCL	81183	84720	88260	91802	95347	98894	10244	10599	10954	11309	11665
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	24452	25433	26414	27395	28376	29357	30338	31320	32301	33282	34263
	UCL	24868	25866	26863	27860	28856	29851	30847	31842	32836	33830	34824
	LCL	24035	25000	25965	26930	27897	28863	29830	30798	31765	32734	33702
Nord-Vest- Model_3	Forecast	15607	16385	17163	17941	18719	19497	20274	21052	21830	22608	23386
	UCL	17412	18224	19036	19847	20657	21467	22276	23085	23893	24701	25508
	LCL	13801	14545	15290	16035	16780	17527	18273	19020	19768	20516	21264
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	3641	3810	3978	4147	4316	4484	4653	4822	4990	5159	5328

	UCL	3880	4052	4224	4396	4568	4740	4912	5084	5256	5428	5600
	LCL	3402	3567	3732	3898	4063	4228	4394	4559	4724	4890	5055
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	1338	1416	1494	1571	1649	1727	1804	1882	1960	2038	2115
	UCL	1445	1524	1604	1683	1763	1842	1921	2001	2080	2160	2239
	LCL	1232	1308	1383	1459	1535	1611	1687	1763	1839	1916	1992
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	5837	6148	6458	6768	7078	7389	7699	8009	8319	8630	8940
	UCL	7179	8045	8781	9451	10078	10675	11248	11803	12344	12872	13389
	LCL	4496	4250	4134	4085	4079	4103	4150	4215	4295	4388	4491
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	1869	1881	1893	1905	1917	1929	1941	1952	1964	1976	1988
	UCL	2068	2259	2482	2732	3008	3307	3627	3966	4325	4701	5095
	LCL	1670	1503	1304	1077	825	551	254	-62	-396	-749	-1119
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	1329	1386	1443	1501	1558	1616	1673	1730	1788	1845	1902
	UCL	1503	1563	1623	1684	1744	1804	1865	1925	1985	2045	2105
	LCL	1155	1209	1263	1318	1372	1427	1481	1536	1590	1645	1700
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	1107	1155	1204	1252	1300	1349	1397	1445	1494	1542	1590
	UCL	1219	1270	1320	1371	1421	1471	1522	1572	1622	1672	1723
	LCL	994	1040	1087	1133	1179	1226	1272	1319	1365	1412	1458
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	9617	10067	10517	10968	11418	11868	12318	12768	13219	13669	14119
	UCL	10620	11075	11531	11987	12442	12898	13353	13809	14264	14720	15175
	LCL	8614	9059	9504	9948	10393	10838	11283	11728	12173	12618	13063
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	1506	1576	1647	1717	1787	1857	1927	1997	2067	2137	2207
	UCL	1606	1677	1749	1820	1892	1963	2035	2106	2177	2249	2320
	LCL	1407	1476	1544	1613	1682	1750	1819	1888	1957	2025	2094
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	2547	2671	2795	2919	3043	3167	3291	3415	3539	3663	3787
	UCL	2811	2937	3062	3187	3312	3438	3563	3688	3814	3939	4064
	LCL	2283	2406	2528	2651	2774	2896	3019	3142	3264	3387	3510

Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	659	687	715	743	772	800	828	857	885	913	941
	UCL	762	791	820	849	878	906	935	964	993	1021	1050
	LCL	555	583	610	638	666	694	721	749	777	805	833
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	807	840	872	904	937	969	1001	1034	1066	1098	1131
	UCL	906	938	971	1004	1037	1070	1103	1135	1168	1201	1234
	LCL	709	741	773	804	836	868	900	932	964	996	1028
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	2108	2212	2316	2420	2524	2628	2732	2836	2940	3044	3148
	UCL	2321	2426	2531	2636	2741	2847	2952	3057	3162	3267	3373
	LCL	1895	1997	2100	2203	2306	2409	2511	2614	2717	2820	2923
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	1998	2090	2181	2273	2364	2456	2547	2639	2730	2822	2913
	UCL	2258	2355	2451	2547	2644	2740	2836	2932	3028	3123	3219
	LCL	1738	1824	1911	1998	2085	2172	2259	2346	2433	2520	2608
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	19375	20157	20938	21719	22500	23282	24063	24844	25625	26407	27188
	UCL	19916	20712	21507	22303	23098	23892	24687	25481	26275	27068	27862
	LCL	18835	19601	20368	21135	21903	22671	23439	24208	24976	25745	26514
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	9883	10438	10994	11549	12105	12660	13216	13771	14326	14882	15437
	UCL	11012	11588	12163	12739	13314	13889	14463	15038	15611	16185	16759
	LCL	8754	9289	9824	10359	10895	11431	11968	12504	13041	13578	14116
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	2130	2252	2375	2497	2619	2742	2864	2987	3109	3231	3354
	UCL	2424	2552	2680	2807	2935	3062	3190	3317	3444	3571	3699
	LCL	1836	1953	2070	2187	2304	2421	2539	2656	2774	2891	3009
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	803	849	894	939	985	1030	1076	1121	1167	1212	1257
	UCL	962	1008	1054	1100	1147	1193	1239	1285	1332	1378	1424
	LCL	645	689	734	778	823	868	912	957	1001	1046	1091
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	2446	2594	2743	2891	3040	3188	3337	3485	3634	3782	3931
	UCL	2854	3011	3167	3323	3479	3634	3790	3945	4101	4256	4411
	LCL	2037	2178	2319	2460	2601	2742	2884	3025	3167	3308	3450

Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	1351	1416	1482	1548	1613	1679	1744	1810	1876	1941	2007
	UCL	1481	1547	1613	1680	1746	1812	1878	1945	2011	2077	2144
	LCL	1221	1286	1351	1416	1481	1545	1610	1675	1740	1805	1870
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	2331	2460	2589	2718	2848	2977	3106	3235	3364	3493	3622
	UCL	2500	2631	2762	2894	3025	3156	3288	3419	3550	3681	3812
	LCL	2162	2289	2416	2543	2670	2797	2924	3051	3178	3305	3432
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	814	859	903	948	992	1037	1081	1126	1170	1214	1259
	UCL	891	937	983	1028	1074	1119	1165	1211	1256	1302	1347
	LCL	738	781	824	867	911	954	997	1040	1084	1127	1170
Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	10289	10758	11226	11694	12163	12631	13099	13568	14036	14505	14973
	UCL	11660	12155	12649	13143	13637	14130	14623	15115	15607	16099	16590
	LCL	8919	9361	9803	10246	10689	11132	11576	12021	12465	12911	13356
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	1419	1507	1595	1683	1771	1859	1947	2035	2123	2211	2299
	UCL	1587	1676	1765	1854	1943	2032	2121	2210	2299	2388	2476
	LCL	1251	1338	1425	1512	1600	1687	1774	1861	1948	2035	2122
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	1440	1502	1564	1625	1687	1749	1811	1872	1934	1996	2057
	UCL	1581	1645	1709	1773	1838	1902	1966	2030	2094	2158	2222
	LCL	1300	1359	1418	1478	1537	1596	1655	1715	1774	1833	1893
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	3596	3719	3841	3964	4087	4210	4333	4456	4578	4701	4824
	UCL	4192	4562	4874	5157	5420	5670	5910	6142	6367	6586	6801
	LCL	3000	2876	2809	2772	2754	2750	2756	2769	2790	2816	2847
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	1696	1785	1875	1965	2055	2144	2234	2324	2414	2503	2593
	UCL	2022	2246	2440	2617	2784	2943	3097	3246	3392	3534	3674
	LCL	1370	1324	1311	1313	1326	1346	1372	1402	1436	1472	1512
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	826	867	907	948	988	1029	1069	1110	1150	1191	1231
	UCL	946	987	1029	1070	1111	1152	1193	1234	1275	1316	1357
	LCL	706	746	786	826	866	906	946	986	1026	1066	1105

Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	1007	1053	1100	1147	1193	1240	1286	1333	1380	1426	1473
	UCL	1143	1246	1336	1419	1498	1574	1647	1718	1788	1857	1925
	LCL	870	861	864	874	889	906	926	948	971	996	1021
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	24289	25474	26658	27842	29027	30211	31395	32580	33764	34948	36133
	UCL	25344	26555	27766	28976	30185	31395	32603	33811	35019	36226	37433
	LCL	23235	24392	25550	26709	27868	29027	30187	31348	32509	33671	34833
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	11310	11953	12595	13238	13881	14524	15166	15809	16452	17095	17737
	UCL	12232	12891	13550	14208	14866	15524	16181	16839	17496	18153	18810
	LCL	10387	11014	11641	12268	12896	13523	14151	14780	15408	16036	16665
Arges-Model_34	Forecast	3628	3855	4083	4310	4538	4765	4992	5220	5447	5674	5902
	UCL	3936	4169	4402	4635	4868	5101	5333	5566	5798	6031	6263
	LCL	3320	3541	3763	3985	4207	4429	4651	4873	5096	5318	5541
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	838	887	935	984	1032	1081	1130	1178	1227	1275	1324
	UCL	932	981	1030	1079	1128	1177	1226	1275	1324	1373	1423
	LCL	744	792	840	889	937	985	1033	1081	1129	1177	1225
Dâmbovita- Model_36	Forecast	1904	2015	2127	2238	2350	2461	2573	2684	2796	2907	3019
	UCL	2057	2169	2282	2394	2506	2618	2731	2843	2955	3067	3180
	LCL	1750	1861	1972	2083	2193	2304	2415	2526	2636	2747	2858
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	853	918	983	1048	1113	1178	1243	1308	1373	1438	1503
	UCL	934	1049	1171	1300	1435	1576	1721	1872	2027	2186	2350
	LCL	773	788	795	796	791	780	764	744	719	689	655
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	749	788	827	865	904	943	981	1020	1059	1097	1136
	UCL	819	858	897	936	975	1014	1053	1092	1131	1170	1209
	LCL	680	718	756	795	833	871	910	948	987	1025	1063
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	2588	2724	2861	2998	3134	3271	3407	3544	3681	3817	3954
	UCL	2960	3251	3506	3742	3967	4183	4393	4597	4798	4995	5189
	LCL	2215	2198	2216	2253	2302	2359	2422	2491	2564	2640	2719

Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	721	760	800	840	879	919	958	998	1038	1077	1117
	UCL	824	906	979	1046	1110	1172	1232	1290	1348	1404	1460
	LCL	617	614	621	633	648	666	685	706	728	751	774
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	13560	14279	14998	15717	16436	17155	17874	18593	19313	20032	20751
	UCL	15135	15883	16630	17377	18124	18870	19616	20361	21106	21851	22595
	LCL	11985	12675	13366	14057	14749	15441	16133	16826	17519	18212	18906
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	10652	11193	11733	12273	12814	13354	13894	14435	14975	15515	16056
	UCL	12163	12731	13299	13867	14434	15000	15567	16132	16698	17263	17828
	LCL	9142	9654	10167	10680	11194	11708	12222	12737	13252	13768	14284
Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	2895	3055	3216	3377	3537	3698	3858	4019	4180	4340	4501
	UCL	3168	3441	3689	3923	4148	4367	4581	4792	4999	5204	5407
	LCL	2622	2669	2743	2830	2927	3029	3136	3247	3360	3477	3595
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	15379	16053	16726	17400	18073	18747	19421	20094	20768	21442	22115
	UCL	15846	16538	17230	17921	18611	19301	19991	20680	21368	22057	22744
	LCL	14912	15567	16223	16879	17536	18193	18851	19509	20168	20827	21486
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	6898	7256	7613	7971	8328	8686	9043	9401	9758	10116	10473
	UCL	7636	8299	8891	9447	9978	10493	10995	11488	11972	12449	12920
	LCL	6161	6212	6335	6495	6678	6878	7091	7314	7544	7782	8026
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	1957	2067	2176	2286	2395	2505	2614	2724	2833	2943	3052
	UCL	2222	2441	2634	2814	2986	3152	3314	3471	3626	3778	3929
	LCL	1693	1693	1719	1757	1804	1857	1915	1976	2040	2107	2175
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	1172	1228	1283	1338	1393	1449	1504	1559	1614	1670	1725
	UCL	1257	1347	1429	1507	1583	1656	1728	1798	1868	1937	2006
	LCL	1088	1108	1136	1169	1204	1241	1280	1320	1361	1402	1444
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	899	941	982	1024	1065	1107	1148	1190	1231	1273	1314
	UCL	1000	1083	1156	1225	1290	1353	1414	1474	1532	1590	1647
	LCL	799	799	808	823	841	861	882	906	930	955	981

Olt-Model_49	Forecast	1102	1172	1243	1314	1385	1456	1527	1597	1668	1739	1810
	UCL	1221	1294	1367	1440	1513	1586	1659	1732	1805	1878	1950
	LCL	982	1050	1119	1188	1256	1325	1394	1463	1532	1601	1669
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	1795	1879	1964	2049	2133	2218	2302	2387	2472	2556	2641
	UCL	1994	2161	2309	2447	2579	2706	2829	2950	3069	3186	3302
	LCL	1595	1598	1619	1650	1688	1730	1776	1824	1874	1927	1980
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	8890	9365	9839	10314	10789	11264	11738	12213	12688	13163	13637
	UCL	10073	10569	11066	11562	12057	12553	13048	13542	14037	14531	15025
	LCL	7707	8160	8613	9067	9520	9975	10429	10884	11339	11794	12250
Arad-Model_52	Forecast	2263	2373	2484	2594	2704	2815	2925	3035	3146	3256	3366
	UCL	2477	2589	2702	2814	2926	3038	3150	3262	3374	3486	3598
	LCL	2049	2157	2266	2374	2483	2591	2700	2809	2917	3026	3134
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	906	947	987	1027	1067	1108	1148	1188	1228	1268	1309
	UCL	1043	1084	1125	1166	1207	1248	1289	1330	1371	1412	1453
	LCL	769	809	848	888	927	967	1006	1046	1085	1125	1165
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	1724	1818	1911	2004	2097	2191	2284	2377	2470	2563	2657
	UCL	1942	2039	2136	2233	2331	2428	2525	2622	2719	2815	2912
	LCL	1507	1596	1686	1775	1864	1953	2043	2132	2222	2311	2401
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	3749	3957	4164	4372	4579	4787	4994	5202	5409	5617	5824
	UCL	4520	5047	5499	5913	6303	6675	7033	7381	7721	8054	8380
	LCL	2979	2867	2830	2830	2856	2899	2955	3022	3097	3179	3268

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